

Aquatic Fungi in Nature

– Memory Game

Are you ready to talk about aquatic fungi in outreach or teaching?

Here is a simple tool – ready to print images to use for the classic game Memory (also called Concentration, Matching Game). This card set is specifically designed to introduce the aquatic fungi in an ecological context. By selecting different cards and talking points, one can use the cards in many ways.

- **What are aquatic fungi?**
 - Select cards to use that represent some of the diversity of aquatic fungi ([Ascomycetes](#), [Basidiomycete](#), [Chytridiomycete](#)) and their ecological roles (decomposers, pathogens). For example you can use cards like Aquatic-mushroom, Fungi_spores1, Fungi_spores2, Mycelium, Maple-leaf, Chytrid, Phytoplankton, Caddisfly-larvae, School-of-fish.
- **What is the role of aquatic fungi in streams?**
 - Discuss how aquatic fungi contribute to decomposition in streams and their contributions to stream food webs. Use cards such as Fungi_spores1, Fungi_spores2, School-of-fish, Maple-leaf, Mycelium, Buffer zone (with woody debris), Caddisfly-larvae, Dragonfly-larvae, School-of-fish.
- **How do aquatic fungi impact life on land?**
 - Combine cards such as Fungi_spores1, Fungi_spores2, School-of-fish, Maple-leaf, Mycelium, Caddisfly-larvae, Dragonfly-larvae, Caddisfly-adult, Dragonfly, Wagtail, Spiderweb.
- **Conservation messages:**
 - Everything is connected.
 - Healthy and diverse aquatic ecosystems, including aquatic fungi, are needed to conserve birds and fish.
 - Healthy and diverse terrestrial ecosystems are needed to protect and conserve aquatic ecosystems.
 - Aquatic fungi are vital parts of healthy and diverse aquatic ecosystems.

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The cards:

Image card	About	Discussion points/questions adjust for age, existing knowledge, communication goal, etc.
Aquatic mushroom	The only described species of aquatic mushroom, Psathyrella aquatica	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Have you ever seen a mushroom in the water? • Very few aquatic fungi make mushrooms. • Sexual reproduction (spores produced by meiosis)
Buffer zone	A rocky shore with a maple tree and a log in the water	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What happens to the leaves and branches that fall into the water? • Aquatic fungi can be found in all aquatic ecosystems (streams, lakes, ponds, ocean etc.).
Caddisfly adult	Adult caddisfly	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How do aquatic fungi help feed spiders/birds? • Caddisfly adults fly and live in the terrestrial environment. They do not eat as adults.
Caddisfly larva	Larval caddisfly	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Larval caddisflies are aquatic. Some are leaf "shredders" which get carbon and nutrients from leaves that aquatic fungi are growing on.
Chytrid	A chytrid sporangium (containing spores) and rhizoids.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Have you heard of the fungus that is killing the frogs? • Have you heard about the "Mycoloop"? • Did you know that some fungi can swim?
Dragonfly	Adult dragonfly	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adult dragon flies live in the terrestrial environment.
Dragonfly larva	Larval dragonfly	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Larval dragonflies are aquatic predators which can eat other animals. • Aquatic fungi support the food webs that feed the prey of the dragonflies.
Fungi Spores 1	Diverse fungal spores. Primarily aquatic hyphomycetes. The spores on the right represent an aeroaquatic fungi and an aquatic ascomycete .	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What happens to the leaves that fall into streams? • Did you know that aquatic fungi are the dominant microbial decomposers of leaves in streams? • The aquatic hyphomycetes are produced by mitosis (asexually), so they are 'just like' the fungus that produced them. • The shapes and features of different spores can help with their dispersal and their ability to "stick" to new substrates (leaves, wood, plants...).
Fungi Spores 2	Diverse spores of aquatic ascomycetes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Most known aquatic fungi are ascomycetes. They don't make "mushrooms". • Aquatic ascomycetes are found in the ocean, lakes, ponds, streams, bogs, etc. • These spores are called ascospores. They are produced through meiosis and sexual reproduction.
Maple leaf	Maple leaf. Example of a leaf that can fall into a stream and be decomposed by aquatic hyphomycetes.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Did you know that aquatic fungi are the dominant microbial decomposers of leaves in streams? • Aquatic fungi make enzymes that can break down tough plant materials like cellulose and lignin. In our diets we call this "fiber". • Aquatic insects are "helped" by aquatic fungi, which make it easier to get carbon and nutrients from the plant materials.
Mycelia	Representation of fungal 'filaments', hyphae, mycelia .	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What do you think aquatic fungi look like? • Many fungi produce mycelia, which are microscopic and grow into the leaves, wood, or other substrate the fungus will obtain its "food" (carbon and nutrients) from.

Phytoplankton	Planktonic organisms that do photosynthesis (obtain energy from sunlight).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Phytoplankton is abundant in oceans and lakes. Chytrids and phytoplankton are key components of the Mycocoop.
School of fish	Group of fish	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aquatic fungi are important in food webs. • How does carbon and nutrients from leaves and wood get transferred to fish?
Spiderweb	Web of spider	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Flying adult insects that had development stages in water move carbon and nutrients out of the aquatic ecosystems and back to terrestrial ecosystems. • Flying insects can be trapped in the webs of spiders. • How do aquatic fungi help feed spiders?
Wagtail	White wagtail , <i>Motacilla alba</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Flying adult insects that had development stages in water move carbon and nutrients out of the aquatic ecosystems and back to terrestrial ecosystems. • Flying insects can be eaten by birds and bats. • How do aquatic fungi help feed birds?

Getting ready:

- 1) Print 2 copies of the cards you choose to use.
- 2) Cut out the images.
- 2) Fix the printed images to sturdy square substrates using adhesive (for example, wooden squares sold in craft outlets for making coasters) to make "memory cards".

NOTE) The images will become worn faster if they are used on a hard surface, reducing the useable lifetime of the cards. It is suggested to play on a tablecloth or other buffered surface. Alternatively, one can apply an environmentally friendly, non-toxic and child-friendly "varnish" if such a product is available.

How to play:

- 1) Turn all the cards so the images are facing down. Arrange in rows.
- 2) Taking turns among players, each player turns over 2 memory cards to make the images visible to all players. The goal is to find matching images.
 - If the images match, the player removes the cards from the board and places them on a pile near themselves. They can then proceed to turn over 2 more cards. This continues until the player turns over cards that do not match.
 - If the cards do not match, the player puts the cards back in their original places, image facing downward. It then becomes the next player's turn.
- 3) The player collecting the most matching pairs wins!

Tips for use in outreach and teaching:

- People of all ages enjoy this game. Children like to play other children, their adult supervisors, or outreach volunteers. In our experience, adults also enjoy playing! Depending on your outreach event or teaching situation, you can promote or support different combinations of players.
- We suggest that an outreach volunteer or teacher either participates in or supervises the matches. This way, teachable moments can be found and used to teach about the biology of the elements on the cards. For example:
 - When a matching pair is found, one can ask what the picture represents or how it is related to another pair that was found previously.
 - Wait until the end of the match and use the cards to support discussion of what the images show and how they relate to each other.
- Adjust your strategy for communication based on the existing knowledge of the participant and their accompanying group (when appropriate).
- If you plan to use all 15 designs, you will have 30 cards total. This can be too many for practical use (space needed to play the game, challenge level of the game) but also may complicate your messaging.

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